

STUDYING THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE CREATIVE ABILITIES OF CHILDREN USING THE ANALYSIS OF THE CORRELATION COEFFICIENT

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KEYWORDS

creative ability, correlation coefficient, Likert scale, monotonic effect, power of influence, family environment, predict, Preschool educational organizations, evaluation method, algorithm.

ABSTRACT

Creative abilities play a pivotal role in a child's cognitive development, influencing their problem-solving skills, adaptability, and future success. This study aimed to explore the factors that affect creative abilities in children through the analysis of correlation coefficients. The correlation coefficient of the influencing factors for the creative ability to master activities, knowledge, understanding at the stage of development of the child's knowledge was studied, evaluation method and algorithm were developed. N_i parameters selected as factors influencing children's creative ability the power to monotonically influence the outcome ρ_R was measured. N_k parameters are processed according to the Likert scale, the formulas of the correlation coefficient were used to calculate the influence of the $A_{N_i,j}$ matrix on the R_j matrix. The correlation coefficient analysis revealed substantial influences of age, interest in activities, teacher's skills, and family environment on children's creative abilities. These factors demonstrated strong associations, emphasizing their significant impact on nurturing creative potential in children.

INTRODUCTION

Providing good education to students in pre-school educational institutions (PEI), take classes according to their interests, training of educators, Effective training within the framework of the state program remains one of the issues on the agenda[1]. In addition, predicting whether or not children will master the activities specified in PEIs ensures quality education. [2]–[4]. In order to predict the creative ability of preschool children, the considered $N_i, i = 1..7$ parameters are considered to be the quality of input parameters of neural networks[5].

The purpose of the research is to study the correlational effects of factors affecting children's creative ability. Each of the $N_i, i = 1..7$ parameters mentioned has a different effect on the result. Knowing the most influential parameters, It

gives a high result in training by educators in PEIs. By working on the N_k parameter with exactly the highest value with children with learning disabilities, it is possible to increase the student's mastery.

E. J. Kang used Hierarchical Linear Models (HLM) to examine the relationship between the factors influencing the creative ability of 5-year-old children and the relationship between the teacher and the teacher[6]. As a result of his research, he emphasized that children's creative abilities are higher in exemplary kindergartens than in average kindergartens. Moreover, this situation was also observed in educators. That is, exemplary kindergartens with excellent curricula and conditions scored better than average kindergartens.

In earlier studies, scientists divided the factors affecting creativity into four parts: "person", "product", "process" and "press"[7]. Personality means that it depends on the emotional characteristics and personal experiences of a person as a factor affecting creative ability. The product notes that these creative products include innovative, valuable products and inventions that are beneficial to society. The creative process is described as focusing on creative ways of synthesizing ideas and adding new ideas to existing knowledge. The press has also focused on the importance of environments influencing individual or community creativity.

In particular, when it comes to the creative ability of children, the main attention should be paid to the individual creative potential of the child and the process of creative expression. In other words, more attention should be paid to children's cognitive abilities, as well as to psychological factors such as personality traits and emotional development[8]. Children's creativity consists of interactions between personal characteristics and social environment[9].

Recently, scientists have begun to pay more attention to children's education. During the analysis of the conducted literature, it can be noted that family environment, activities of the institution, activities outside the institution, environments that encourage the independence of students, the role of games and games, flexible use of time, respectful relations between children and educators, teams and use of social networks can be cited[6]. In addition, it is considered that the children's age, gender and social origin have an influence on learning the activities. Targeting children with activities that match their interests and predicting their ability to master the activities will do well[2]. At the same time, many scientific works have been carried out by world scientists to determine the factors affecting children's creative ability.

STATEMENT OF THE ISSUE

In this study, we consider the following parameters as affecting children's creative abilities.

N₁ Age: Age often correlates with shifts in cognitive development. Younger children may

display spontaneous creativity, while older children might engage in more complex forms of creative thinking, influenced by accumulated knowledge and experiences.

N₂ Gender: Research suggests that gender can affect creative expression due to societal norms and expectations. However, creativity is not inherently tied to gender and should be fostered regardless of gender identity.

N₃ Interest in Training: A child's intrinsic motivation to engage in creative activities can greatly impact their creative abilities. Children who actively seek out and participate in training that stimulates their curiosity and imagination are likely to develop stronger creative skills.

N₄ Family Size: Family size might influence a child's creative abilities through interpersonal interactions. In smaller families, children might receive more focused attention, fostering creativity. In larger families, diverse perspectives and interactions could contribute to creative thinking.

N₅ Social Origins: A child's social background, including socioeconomic status and cultural context, can shape their exposure to various experiences, resources, and opportunities. These influences play a role in fostering creativity through different pathways.

N₆ Educator Skill: Teachers and educators who possess strong creative teaching methods, encourage critical thinking, and create a stimulating learning environment can significantly impact a child's creative development.

N₇ Family Environment: The family environment, including parental involvement, support for creative expression, and access to resources like books and art supplies, can significantly influence a child's creative growth.

$$N = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} N_1 = \text{age,} \\ N_2 = \text{gender,} \\ N_3 = \text{interest in training,} \\ N_4 = \text{family size,} \\ N_5 = \text{educator skill,} \\ N_6 = \text{the skill of the educator,} \\ N_7 = \text{family environment.} \end{array} \right\}$$

We assume that each of the $N_i, i = 1..7$ parameters affects the creative ability of children. Turkish scientist N. Karaca and other scientists noted that age and gender are not important for children's creative ability[10]. However, $N_i, i = \{1,2\}$ values were obtained to compare the remaining values.

225 values obtained from pupils of pre-school educational organizations in the form of a questionnaire are expressed in the form of matrix $A_{N_i,j}, i = 1..7, j = 1..225$ [11].

The extent to which the mentioned parameters influence children's creative ability can be determined using the Spearman correlation coefficient.

METHODS

In the realm of parameter analysis, two widely employed methods are Spearman's correlation and Pearson's correlation. Spearman's correlation evaluates the magnitude and direction of the connection between two variables, irrespective of their linear or non-linear nature. It's particularly suitable when examining relationships that may not conform to linear patterns, making it the preferred choice for investigating the multifaceted factors influencing children's creativity. On the other hand, Pearson's correlation is geared towards gauging the strength of a linear association in paired data. Given that the intricate factors shaping children's creative abilities often exhibit complex, non-linear dynamics, Spearman's correlation is better suited for capturing the nuanced interactions within this context. Thus, by opting for Spearman's correlation, researchers enhance the precision of their analysis in unraveling the intricate web of influences on children's creative development[12].

The Spearman correlation coefficient was determined by the following formula,

$$r_R = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_i d_i^2}{n(n^2-1)} \quad (1)$$

Here, n is the number of parameters, and d is the difference between the parameters.

It usually accepts values in the range $r_R \in [-1; 1]$. If $r_R > 0$, the relationship between two

parameters is positive, if $r_R = 0$, there is no relationship, if $r_R < 0$, it means a negative relationship. In addition, any value close to 0 is classified as weak.

The values of the given array $A_{N_i,j}, i = 1..7, j = 1..225$ consist of the set of real positive numbers. Array elements are sorted to determine the Spearman correlation coefficient. For this, the given array elements are written based on the following formula.

$$M_i = \sum_{i=1, c=1, s=s+i}^{j+1} A_{i,j+1}^{\max_{i,j+1} \sum_{k=i}^j \text{if}(\max=A_k; s=s+k, c=c+1, m=k)} \quad (2)$$

Here, s is the sum of the indices of maxima of array elements $A_{N_i,j}$, c is the number of maxima, and k is the index of the last maxima.

In the process of sorting, array elements of equal value are divided and valued like $T_r = \left\{ \frac{s}{c} \right\}$ if they form an array $T_r (r \geq 1)$. Based on the above formulas, array $B_{N_i,j}, i = 1..7, j = 1..225$ is formed by sorting the elements of array $A_{N_i,j}$.

$$B_{l,j} = \sum_{l=i-1, i=i+m}^m \frac{s}{c} \quad (3)$$

Here, m is the last maximum value found.

$$B_{N_i,j} = \sum_{i=1}^{j+1} M_i, B_{l,j} \quad (4)$$

To measure the influence of each element of $N_i, i = 1..7$ parameters on the array $R_j, j = 1..225$, R_j array is also sorted based on (4) formulas to form $R_j^t, j = 1..225$ array.

The square of the absolute value of the difference of arrays $B_{N_i,j}$ and R_j^t is equal to d_i^2 in the formula (1).

$$d_i = B_{N_i,j} - R_j^t$$

Some N_k parameters assign a unique integer value to each category. It essentially converts the categories into numerical labels, allowing algorithms to work with them.

The following were obtained using the formula (1).

$$r_R^{N_1} = 0,61, r_R^{N_2} = 0,27, r_R^{N_3} = 0,65, r_R^{N_4} = 0,48,$$

$$r_R^{N_5} = 0,39, r_R^{N_6} = 0,57, r_R^{N_7} = 0,55$$

1-fig. Analysis of the correlation coefficient of factors influencing children's creative ability.

RESULT

The diagram (fig. 1) visually represents the extent to which the factors influencing children's creativity manifest their relationships. Among the chosen parameters, the strength of associations is depicted by the correlation coefficient values, and the diagram offers an insightful overview of their interplay. Notably, the highest value observed is $r_R^{N_3} = 0,65$, corresponding to factor N_3 . This indicates a strong positive correlation between this particular factor and children's creative abilities, highlighting its influential role in fostering creativity.

Moreover, factors N_1 , N_6 , and N_7 also exhibit significant outcomes in the diagram. Their satisfactory results suggest that these parameters possess notable connections with children's creative abilities, albeit at slightly lower correlation coefficients. The visual representation of these correlations aids in understanding the relative impact of each factor on the overall creative development of children. The diagram's clarity facilitates the identification of trends and patterns among the influencing factors, contributing to a comprehensive comprehension of how age, interest in activities, teacher's skills, and family environment collectively contribute to nurturing creative potential. While the highest correlation emphasizes the significance of a specific factor, the noteworthy outcomes for other parameters underscore the intricate web of influences at play.

The diagram serves as an effective tool for intuitively grasping the magnitude and direction of relationships between factors and children's creative abilities. It provides a holistic view of their relative strengths, enabling educators, researchers, and policymakers to make informed decisions when designing strategies to enhance children's creative development.

Based on the obtained results and statistical data, we propose the following algorithm.

$$D = \begin{cases} \text{"good"}, & \text{if } \{60 < r_R^{N_3} \leq 100\} \\ \text{"satisfactory"}, & \text{if } \{30 < r_R^{N_3} \leq 60\} \\ \text{"unsatisfactory"}, & \text{if } \{0 < r_R^{N_3} \leq 30\} \end{cases}$$

CONCLUSION

Among the selected parameters analyzed to predict and determine children's creative abilities, N_3 , N_1 , N_6 , and N_7 emerge with the highest values, as observed in the research findings. These parameters correspond to age, interest in training, skills of the educator, and family environment. This reveals their pivotal role in significantly influencing children's creative abilities in comparison to other factors. The robust correlation coefficients associated with these parameters indicate their substantial impact on fostering creative potential in children.

Furthermore, the integration of these findings into educational practices holds promising implications. In instances where creative abilities require enhancement, pre-school educational institutions (PEI) tutors can utilize the provided algorithm. By identifying and focusing on children with lower mastery levels, the tutors can tailor their instructional strategies to address specific needs. Moreover, adopting a more intensive approach towards parameters evaluated as "good" in the educational process can considerably enhance the quality of children's learning experiences. This personalized pedagogical approach acknowledges the diverse influences that shape creative development and aims to provide tailored support to each child.

The developed algorithm's versatility extends to predictive applications. By leveraging the algorithm's insights, educators can forecast children's creative abilities based on the identified

parameters. This proactive approach not only informs educational planning but also assists in devising strategies that cultivate creativity early on, nurturing the potential for innovative thinking in the long term.

In conclusion, the convergence of the research outcomes underscores the significance of age, interest in training, educator skills, and family environment in shaping children's creative abilities. The algorithm's implementation empowers educators to address individual needs effectively, fostering creative development in those who require additional attention while elevating the educational quality for those already excelling. Furthermore, the predictive aspect of the algorithm accentuates its potential to contribute to more holistic and informed approaches in nurturing children's creative potential, ensuring a well-rounded and impactful educational journey.

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